

Forecasting creditworthiness in credit scoring using machine learning methods

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ABSTRACT

This article provides an overview of modern machine learning methods in the context of their active use in credit scoring, with particular attention to the following algorithms: light gradient boosting machine (LGBM) classifier, logistic regression (LR), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), decision tree (DT) classifier, gradient boosting classifier and extreme gradient boosting (XGB) classifier. Each of the methods mentioned is subject to careful analysis to evaluate their applicability and effectiveness in predicting credit risk. The article examines the advantages and limitations of each method, identifying their impact on the accuracy and reliability of borrower creditworthiness assessments. Current trends in machine learning and credit scoring are also covered, warning of challenges and discussing prospects. The analysis highlights the significant contributions of methods such as LGBM classifier, LR, LDA, DT classifier, gradient boosting classifier and XGB classifier to the development of modern credit scoring practices, highlighting their potential for improving the accuracy and reliability of borrower creditworthiness forecasts in the financial services industry. Additionally, the article discusses the importance of careful selection of machine learning models and the need to continually update methodology in light of the rapidly changing nature of the financial market.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world of finance, where competition in the lending market [1]–[3] is constantly growing, the relevance of developing effective methods for predicting creditworthiness is high. The accuracy and reliability of such methods are key factors for financial institutions seeking to minimize risk and ensure the sustainability of their loan portfolios. Light gradient boosting machine (LGBM) classifier [4]–[6], logistic regression [7]–[9], linear discriminant analysis [10]–[13], decision tree classifier [13], [14], gradient boosting classifier [15]–[17] and extreme gradient boosting (XGB) classifier [18], [19] are a variety of machine training, each with its own unique characteristics and applications. Their use in credit scoring [20]–[22] opens up new opportunities for improving the accuracy of forecasts, especially when working with large volumes of data and complex credit models. In this study, we will also address issues of model

interpretability, computational complexity, and potential limitations. These aspects play an important role in the implementation of research results in real financial practices. Research into creditworthiness using machine learning methods is not only of academic interest, but also has direct application value for financial institutions, insurance companies and other market players. It is expected that the results of this study can serve as a basis for optimizing decision-making processes in the lending industry and provide more effective risk management.

Koc *et al.* [23] explore the role of credit ratings in assessing financial stability and the criteria for issuing a loan. They review eight machine learning methods, including support vector machines (SVM), Gaussian naive Bayes, decision trees (DT), random forest (RF), XGB, k-nearest neighbors (KNN), multi-layer perceptron (MLP), and logistic regression (LR). The main objective of the study is to demonstrate the beneficial application of these methods for predicting loan default risk and identifying influencing factors. The paper provides an extensive comparison evaluating which machine learning models perform better with and without their own feature selection method. Jiang *et al.* [24] explore the problem of credit scoring with a focus on identifying anomalies and maintaining order in financial transactions. They highlight the class imbalance problem that arises from the limited number of default records in financial data. To address this problem, the authors analyze various classical approaches to learning from imbalanced data, including resampling methods, cost-of-error strategies, and the use of generative adversarial networks (GANs) as a tool for learning from imbalanced data.

Abdoli *et al.* [25] examine the importance of automated credit scoring as a risk management tool for banks and financial institutions, noting its attractiveness in recent decades. They highlight that the unbalanced nature of credit scoring datasets, as well as feature heterogeneity, pose challenges to developing efficient models that can generalize to previously unseen data. The paper proposes the bagging supervised autoencoder classifier (BSAC), a model that combines the benefits of supervised learning for autoencoders and a bagging mechanism to handle heterogeneities in feature space, and the results of extensive experiments confirm the superiority and robustness of the proposed method in predicting the outcome of loan applications.

The relevance of the topic of predicting the creditworthiness of credit scoring using machine learning methods cannot be overestimated in the light of modern challenges in the financial industry. With the increasing volume of data and the variety of factors affecting the financial situation of borrowers, standard methods of assessing creditworthiness are not effective enough. The use of advanced machine learning methods provides the opportunity not only for more accurate forecasting, but also for deeper data analysis, which in turn helps to identify early signs of financial risks. Solutions based on LGBM classifier, LR, LDA, DT classifier, gradient boosting classifier and XGB classifier promise improved credit scoring results, which are critical to ensuring the sustainability of financial institutions and reducing the likelihood of financial crises.

2. METHOD

The purpose of this study is a comparative analysis of machine learning methods for predicting creditworthiness in credit scoring. We set ourselves the task of determining the optimal method among LGBM classifier, LR, LDA, DT classifier, gradient boosting classifier and XGB classifier, as well as evaluating their effectiveness based on standard classification metrics. As a basis for our research, we used a large and diverse data set that included information about borrowers' financial situation, credit history, social factors and other relevant variables. This dataset provides us with the opportunity to more comprehensively analyze and evaluate the proposed methods. Before applying machine learning methods, careful data preprocessing was carried out, including handling missing values, encoding categorical features, normalizing numerical data, and processing outliers. This stage allows you to ensure the correctness and stability of the models.

LGBM is a gradient amplification method optimized for efficient work with large volumes of data. This method draws attention to taking into account unbalanced classes, which is an important aspect in credit scoring problems. Logistic regression is a classic binary classification method based on a logistic function. We use it in the context of credit scoring to assess the likelihood of a borrower's creditworthiness and make a decision based on that likelihood. LDA is a linear discriminant analysis method designed to maximize differences between classes. In credit scoring, this method can be effective for highlighting key features that affect creditworthiness. Decision tree classifiers provide a visual representation of decision making and are capable of capturing complex relationships in data. We use this method to identify the structure of criteria that influence the forecasting of creditworthiness. The gradient boosting classifier allows the construction of ensembles of decision trees, which can improve the predictive power of the model. We'll explore its use in credit scoring and evaluate how it handles complex data structures. XGB is a gradient boosting implementation that provides additional optimizations and regularizations. We will look at its impact on the accuracy of credit forecasts.

To objectively compare machine learning methods, we used standard metrics such as accuracy, recall, precision and F1-measure. These metrics evaluate both the overall performance of the models and their ability to correctly identify borrowers with problematic credit histories. We conducted a series of experiments, training each model on the training set and testing on the test set. The results are analyzed using evaluation metrics to identify the best methods that can effectively solve the problem of creditworthiness forecasting.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To build the models, we used the home credit dataset from *kaggle.com*, containing 65 columns. The data set includes a column called TARGET, which represents the target variable (1 - customer with payment difficulties: he was late in payment, 0 - all other cases). Column names and descriptions are given in Table 1 (see in Appendix).

In experiments with credit prediction in a binary classification task, we applied a common thresholding method to convert predicted probabilities (y_{pred}) into binary class labels. This process is carried out using a threshold set at 0.5: probabilities equal to or greater than 0.5 are rounded to 1 (positive class), while probabilities below 0.5 are rounded to 0 (negative class). This approach allows us to obtain clear categories of object membership in classes, which simplifies the interpretation of classification results and prevents ambiguities associated with threshold values. In the considered methods (LGBM classifier, LR, LDA, DT classifier, gradient boosting classifier and XGB classifier), the key metrics for each of them were evaluated after applying a set threshold, as shown in Figure 1(a) to (f), where the results are present: ROC_AUC, accuracy, precision, recall, specificity and F1-score. These results reflect the performance of each method after applying a standard threshold of 0.5. This probability rounding technique plays an important role in the construction of binary classification models, ensuring their interpretability and applicability in various subject areas, including credit scoring.

Figure 1. Metric results after adjustment by methods: (a) ROC_AUC, (b) accuracy, (c) precision, (d) recall, (e) specificity, and (f) F1-score

Based on the analysis of the graphs in Figure 1, we can conclude that negative classes were correctly predicted in most cases, which is confirmed by high specificity values. However, the need to adjust the decision threshold is an integral step in optimizing models, especially when balancing between false positives and false negatives. In this context, it was decided to conduct experiments with different threshold values and evaluate their impact on key metrics such as precision (Precision), recall (Recall) and F1-measure. Using different thresholds for classification allows you to tune the sensitivity of the model to specific classes in accordance with the requirements of the application domain. This is especially important in the context of credit scoring, where the weight of various types of errors can be critical. By finding the optimal threshold, a balance can be achieved between minimizing false positives and false negatives, which in turn will improve the quality of the model's predictions, as shown in Figure 2(a) to (f), which presents metric results after adjustment by methods: ROC_AUC, accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, and F1-score.

Figure 2. Metric results after adjustment by methods: (a) ROC_AUC, (b) accuracy, (c) precision, (d) recall, (e) specificity, and (f) F1-score

Experiments with different decision thresholds provide additional exploratory evidence, expanding our understanding of the model's sensitivity to different levels of decision confidence. Analysis of the confusion matrix in Figure 3, or error matrix, based on different thresholds allows you to look in more detail at the impact of changing the threshold on the quality of classification. This approach is important for refining the model settings in accordance with the specific requirements and preferences of the business. The results obtained can serve as the basis for more accurate and flexible adjustment of the model within the framework of credit scoring requirements.

In the figures, the metrics of the decision tree classifier model for the training and test data sets remained unchanged. This is because the tree returns predictions not as probabilities, but as integers. The accuracy of the models is high in the original tables with a threshold of 0.5, since in the data under study the number of one class significantly exceeds the number of another. Models are good at predicting bad customer

data, but bad at predicting good ones. Therefore, it is advisable to rely on other indicators. After adjusting the threshold, the main metrics increased significantly for all models except the decision tree, indicating the positive impact of choosing the right thresholds.

Figure 3. Confusion matrix of XGBoost method

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, analyzing models in the context of credit scoring, six different classification algorithms were examined. Each of these models has demonstrated its unique characteristics and performance, enriching our understanding of their applicability in credit forecasting tasks. The results highlight the outstanding performance of XGB classifier, which stands out among other models in all metrics reviewed, including ROC_AUC, accuracy, F1-score, and specificity. This demonstrates the high performance of XGB classifier in the context of credit scoring and its ability to predict creditworthiness with a high degree of accuracy. Additional research into the variation of decision thresholds when rounding class membership probabilities revealed a significant improvement in the predictive ability of the models. Analyzing metrics such as ROC_AUC, precision, recall, specificity, and F1-score at different thresholds highlights the importance of finding a trade-off between false positives and false negatives. Overall, the results of our study not only enrich the understanding of the performance of various models in credit scoring, but also highlight the importance of careful calibration and selection of optimal thresholds to improve forecasting performance. These findings provide valuable guidance for decision making in the field of credit scoring and in the context of financial risk management.

APPENDIX

Table 1. Data set with descriptions

Column name	Describe
<i>EXT_SOURCE_3</i>	Normalized score from external data source
<i>EXT_SOURCE_1</i>	Normalized score from external data source
<i>EXT_SOURCE_2</i>	Normalized score from external data source
<i>DAYS_BIRTH</i>	Client's age in days at the time of application
<i>AMT_CREDIT</i>	Credit amount of the loan
<i>AMT_ANNUIITY</i>	Loan annuity
<i>AMT_GOODS_PRICE</i>	For consumer loans it is the price of the goods for which the loan is given
<i>OWN_CAR_AGE</i>	Age of client's car
<i>DAYS_EMPLOYED</i>	How many days before the application the person started current employment
<i>DAYS_REGISTRATION</i>	How many days before the application did client change his registration
<i>REGION_POPULATION_RELATIVE</i>	Normalized population of region where client lives (higher number means the client lives in more populated region)
<i>DAYS_ID_PUBLISH</i>	How many days before the application did client change the identity document with which he applied for the loan
<i>AMT_INCOME_TOTAL</i>	Income of the client
<i>DAYS_LAST_PHONE_CHANGE</i>	How many days before application did client change phone
<i>ENTRANCES_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor

Table 1. Data set with descriptions (*continue*)

Column name	Describe
<i>AMT_REQ_CREDIT_BUREAU_YEAR</i>	Number of enquiries to Credit Bureau about the client one day year (excluding last 3 months before application)
<i>YEARS_BUILD_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>AMT_REQ_CREDIT_BUREAU_MON</i>	Number of enquiries to Credit Bureau about the client one month before application (excluding one week before application)
<i>LIVINGAREA_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>COMMONAREA_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>LANDAREA_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>LIVINGAPARTMENTS_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>OBS_30_CNT_SOCIAL_CIRCLE</i>	How many observations of client's social surroundings with observable 30 DPD (days past due) default
<i>FLOORSMAX_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>LIVINGAPARTMENTS_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>LANDAREA_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>LANDAREA_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>NONLIVINGAREA_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>HOOR_APPR_PROCESS_START</i>	Approximately at what hour did the client apply for the loan
<i>REGION_RATING_CLIENT_W_CITY</i>	Our rating of the region where client lives with taking city into account (1,2,3)
<i>LIVINGAPARTMENTS_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>LIVINGAREA_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>CNT_FAM_MEMBERS</i>	How many family members does client have
<i>YEARS_BEGINEXPLUATATION_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>AMT_REQ_CREDIT_BUREAU_QRT</i>	Number of enquiries to Credit Bureau about the client 3 month before application (excluding one month before application)
<i>FLOORSMIN_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>YEARS_BUILD_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>OBS_60_CNT_SOCIAL_CIRCLE</i>	How many observations of client's social surroundings with observable 60 DPD (days past due) default
<i>BASEMENTAREA_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor

Table 1. Data set with descriptions (*continue*)

Column name	Describe
<i>YEARS_BUILD_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>APARTMENTS_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>COMMONAREA_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>BASEMENTAREA_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>NONLIVINGAREA_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>APARTMENTS_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>NONLIVINGAPARTMENTS_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>DEF_60_CNT_SOCIAL_CIRCLE</i>	How many observations of client's social surroundings defaulted on 60 (days past due) DPD
<i>AMT_REQ_CREDIT_BUREAU_WEEK</i>	Number of enquiries to Credit Bureau about the client one week before application (excluding one day before application)
<i>TOTALAREA_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>DEF_30_CNT_SOCIAL_CIRCLE</i>	How many observations of client's social surroundings defaulted on 30 DPD (days past due)
<i>YEARS_BEGINEXPLUATATION_AVG</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>REG_CITY_NOT_LIVE_CITY</i>	Flag if client's permanent address does not match contact address (1=different, 0=same, at city level)
<i>FLAG_DOCUMENT_18</i>	Did client provide document 18
<i>FLAG_DOCUMENT_16</i>	Did client provide document 16
<i>FLAG_DOCUMENT_8</i>	Did client provide document 8
<i>FLAG_WORK_PHONE</i>	Did client provide home phone (1=YES, 0=NO)
<i>YEARS_BEGINEXPLUATATION_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>NONLIVINGAPARTMENTS_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>FLAG_DOCUMENT_3</i>	Did client provide document 3
<i>FLAG_DOCUMENT_6</i>	Did client provide document 6
<i>FLAG_DOCUMENT_14</i>	Did client provide document 14
<i>APARTMENTS_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>BASEMENTAREA_MEDI</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>FLOORSMAX_MODE</i>	Normalized information about building where the client lives, what is average (<i>_AVG suffix</i>), modus (<i>_MODE suffix</i>), median (<i>_MEDI suffix</i>) apartment size, common area, living area, age of building, number of elevators, number of entrances, state of the building, number of floor
<i>FLAG_EMP_PHONE</i>	Did client provide work phone (1=YES, 0=NO)

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